

OLD CEBUANO DAYGUN: TRAVERSING NATIVE ORAL AND HISPANIC TRADITIONS

Maricris B. Lauro, MALit

ABSTRACT

The study is geared around decoding the indigenous and Hispanic traditions present in the *daygun* by looking at characteristics that point to the *daygun's* orality and characteristics that exhibit Hispanic influences. The study looks into the presence of indigenous and Hispanic characteristics exhibited by the *daygun*, along with rhyme scheme and borrowed Hispanic words. To satisfy these sub-problems, the study makes use of the ethnographic research design following the five phases: documentation, transcription, decoding borrowed terms, interpretation, and theorizing. The study finds out that the *daygun*; indeed, exhibit the orality of indigenous poetry manifested in its narrative and descriptive quality, its repetitive and formulaic refrains, its subjectivity and self-referentiality, and the affirmation of the bardic role of the carolers. Meanwhile, the allusions pertaining to the infancy narratives of Jesus, which pervade the *daygun* are a heritage of its rich Hispanic influence. A number of Spanish words used as loan words and derivatives prove that these words have permeated the Cebuano-Visayan language and that, together with the allusions, pervading stereotypes and images, they provide tangible evidence to the marriage of thoughts, nuances, beliefs and traditions exemplified in the hybridity of the *daygun*.

Introduction

When one studies Cebuano culture or heritage, one cannot isolate it from the Cebuano speaker. The ambivalent sense of identity due to several historical obstructions brought about by Western colonization is easily manifested by the modern Cebuano's preference of a second language for everyday expression. The modern Cebuano speaker finds himself torn in expressing oneself accordingly in the language that one is born into, yet the pervasive colonial psyche invades his preference to identify himself and articulate in English.

This study on the *daygun* reconciles with the Cebuano's ambivalent identity. The *daygun sits* at the heart of the indigenous and Hispanic convergence that Santos considers as "hybrid forms that grew out of the fusion of pre-existing intercultural elements"¹ in classifying the Filipino musical repertoire in the article "Constructing a National Identity through Music". In the same article, Santos points out that

The second form consists of genres that were characterized by the fusion of Christian elements and pre-colonial music. This repertoire was mainly embodied in the extra liturgical practices that not only supplemented the liturgical rites of the Roman church, but also drew the spiritual and mystical fervor of indigenous worship into the Filipino version of the Christian religion. This musico-poetic repertoire consists mainly of the *pasyon*, the Lenten chanting of the life and passion of Jesus Christ, as well as song performed on the different major events of the liturgical calendar, e.g. the *aleluya* at Easter, the *alay* for the May flower festival, and the *pastores* and *daygon* for Christmas...²

Clearly, the *daygun* imparts an indispensable and non-tangible cultural heritage characterized by the persisting orality of indigenous poetry while it was permeated by new sensibilities brought about by colonization. To consider Western colonization as a factor in the displacement or the unfamiliar state of Cebuano literature is rather uninformed. In “Constructing a National Identity through Music,” Santos points out, “The national Filipino identity embodies the concept of convergence and intersection of both the indigenous and European traditions.”³ In this light, the Cebuano oral tradition is a tradition no longer displaced but runs parallel with the European as it was enriched in nuances, sensibilities, and experience through colonization. In short, the *daygun* under study illustrates the point of convergence as a tradition of both Filipino and European descent. This convergence enriches the folk tradition owing to its contribution of a more elaborate oral tradition.

Similarly, in “Folk Traditions,” Canave-Diaquino pronounced, “Hispanization was tied up with religious conversion and the people’s thinking was affected, resulting in a hybrid expression tinged with a Latin taste.”⁴ It produced a music connected to and outside the Catholic liturgy very much evident in the *daygun*. As proof, the *daygun* is sung with a tone that takes after most liturgical songs. Similarly, Mojares contends that “Spanish colonization cultivated new themes and sentiments.”⁵ This particular phenomenon enriched the native tradition as well as the “frequent migration of images and tropes from form to form and performance to performance.”⁶ In the case of the study, the Biblical narrative of Christ’s birth is nativized in rendering it using the genre of the *daygun* that lends its form and style largely from the native tradition. Noticeably, the form of the *daygun* takes after the form of most Cebuano indigenous literature whose line ranges from seven to twelve syllables. Both assonantal and end rhyme which are characteristics of both indigenous and Hispanic traditions are evident in the *daygun*.

Meanwhile, the *daygun* being a descendant of the Hispanic and the indigenous, exhibits a repository of common elements and semblances derived from both traditions. To prove such, the study will explore the parallel indigenous characteristics as well as Hispanic influences. Of the characteristics common to indigenous Cebuano poetry, the *daygun* exhibits assonantal rhyme, subjectivity and self-reflexivity, repetition and formulaic refrain and conclusions. Meanwhile the Hispanic traditions that enrich the *daygun* include the presence of the rhyme scheme, borrowed Hispanic words, and a plethora of allusions.

The *daygun* under study are from the district of Catmon Daan, Borbon, a town of Cebu province. According to the carolers, the songs attained popularity in the 1960s but are still sung even until now, particularly in Bali-ang, Licos, Torre, and Basak – the first three being mountain barangays of Danao, while the remaining one is a mountain barangay of Compostela. According to the carolers, the songs recall the stages of the Christmas season culminating with Candlemas (Candelaria on February 2). “Daygun si Hesus,” that concerns the account of the birth of Jesus, is sung during Advent until Christmas Day. “Gabi-i Daku’ng Bulahan” is sung to celebrate Christmas Eve. Originally, “Tulu ka Hari” is rendered with different voice ranges – tenor and bass – and is sung in January to celebrate the finding of the Child Jesus by the three kings, but it is now sung chorally with a combination of male and female voices. Another song, “Kandelaria,” marks the 40th day from the birth of Jesus and is specifically sung to remember the Presentation. Similar *daygun* like “Oras sa Paglakaw,” “Tagbalay,” and “Belen” are also sung interspersed with the longer songs. Meanwhile, the carolers are keen to improvise and cut the songs short to extend their mileage until the next few houses.

Though the *daygun* is still sung today, only a few studies have been made regarding the genre. Mojares has been incessantly quoted, saying that Cebuano poetry is premature and unless

critiques are contributed, then its state may be augmented.⁷ This pronouncement also holds true when considering the state of Cebuano oral tradition. More than satisfying natural curiosity which at first prompted the researcher to pursue this study, it also tries to establish the fact that the experience of Cebuano oral tradition should not prove “familiar and strange”, as Mojares once put it.⁸ It should reconcile the Cebuano to the very tradition that made him – a hybrid of both Hispanic and Filipino.

Statement of the Problem

The study looks into the *daygun* as a continuation of the Cebuano oral tradition while considering the indigenous and the influence of Hispanic traditions. Specifically, it looks into the following:

1. characteristics of indigenous and Hispanic literature present in the *daygun*
2. rhyme scheme and meter; and
3. borrowed Hispanic words

Method

The study makes use of the ethnographic research design divided into the following phases: documentation, transcription of both musical score and lyrics, decoding borrowed words, interpretation, and theorizing.

Phase 1 – Documentation

The documentation process involved video-recording the *daygun* as they were rendered by the carolers on June 22, 2014, Rogelio Malbario, 58, of San Antonio, Sabang, Danao City, as well as Consolacion Nueva, 60, of Mahayahay, Sabang, Danao City. Nueva learned the songs when she was 12 years old and is originally from Tabogon Daan, Catmon, Cebu. Malbario and Nueva are two of the carolers who sing the *daygun* in full. While Nueva sings, Malbario accompanies her on the guitar. Seven songs were sung: “Daygun si Hesus,” “Gabi-i Daku’ng Bulahan,” “Tulu ka Hari,” “Kandelaria,” “Oras sa Paglakaw,” “Tagbalay,” and “Belen.” The first four songs are longer; they usually run for six to seven minutes, while the remaining three songs usually take at least two to three minutes to complete.

Phase 2 – Transcription

The songs were transcribed manually. They were played again and again, listened to, and the lyrics were recorded on paper. Upon completion, the lyrics were accorded musical notation by a MAPE major.

Phase 3 – Decoding Borrowed Terms

The process involved listing unfamiliar Hispanic terms that had permeated in the *daygun*. It looked into loan words, derivatives, forms of address from the Spanish language and contextually defining them within the *daygun*. The process was also useful in determining the Lauro, M. “Old Cebuano Daygun: Traversing Native Oral and Hispanic Traditions.” *STC College Faculty Journal*, Vol XII, May 2015, pp. 13-32.

extent through which the Spanish language was assimilated in the Cebuano-Visayan language. The plethora of borrowed words and the existing rhyme scheme determined the extent to which Hispanization has influenced the oral tradition.

Phase 4 – Interpretation

This phase traced the indigenous and Hispanic characteristics as they are manifested in the *daygun*. To achieve this, the study looked into the commonalities and differences with some characteristics of the *daygun* that paralleled those of oral or indigenous literature as well as the Hispanic counterparts. Specifically, it examined the allusions and metaphors manifested in the *daygun*. It looked into the consistency or faithfulness of the *daygun* with the Christmas story as it is known or written.

Phase 5 – Theorizing

This phase derived new insights from the interpretation and answered the main problem under study. It tried to accommodate the idea that the *daygun* may be considered a genre that brings two poetic traditions together. It accorded the *daygun* a paraliturgical identity bearing a blend of indigenous and Hispanic poetic distinctiveness.

Results and Discussion

The following section presents the findings of the study in its attempt to establish the Cebuano *daygun* as a continuing tradition of both the Hispanic and native Cebuano as opposed to considering it as a continuation of the native tradition whose development is inhibited by Western domination.

Characteristics of the Daygun

It can be recalled that there are seven *daygun* sung at different intervals throughout the Christmas season. “Gabi-i Daku’ng Bulahan,” which is sung on Christmas Eve, narrates the conception of the virgin and the family’s search for lodgings. “Daygun si Hesus” is particularly sung on Christmas Day, yet the song noticeably pays tribute to the virgin as it repeatedly exalts her in her role in the birth of the Savior. Meanwhile, “Tulu Ka Hari” is sung with different male voices – tenor and bass – and is sung on the Feast of the Three Kings. It celebrates the humility of the three kings in prostrating themselves before the child King born to be purposely higher than any king. “Kandelaria” is sung on February 2, exactly forty days after the birth of Jesus. The three remaining *daygun* – “Tagbalay,” “Belen,” and “Oras sa Paglakaw” are sung interspersed with the longer *daygun*.

Narrative and Descriptive Quality of the Daygun

Prior to the discussion of the sub-problems, there are apparent characteristics of the seven *daygun* that affirm the native literature’s orality. The characteristics of the *daygun* being narrative and descriptive, having repetitive and formulaic refrains, as well as being subjective and self-referential, are borrowed from indigenous poetry. The other characteristic that of being

Lauro, M. “Old Cebuano Daygun: Traversing Native Oral and Hispanic Traditions.” *STC College Faculty Journal*, Vol XII, May 2015, pp. 13-32.

allusion-based, is Hispanic. These characteristics occur across the *daygun* despite the differences in their contents.

Highly characteristic of the *daygun* are the words with almost similar meaning juxtaposed with synonymous terms. The striking metaphorical lines are reminiscent of the *kennings* which are poetic synonyms of Old English *Beowulf*. However, in the succeeding lines, the use of poetic synonyms departs from a metaphorical to either a hyperbolic or conceptual comparison, probably to instill “a sense of drama” or to infuse “word-pictures” to make the narrative more vivid (England in Literature). This is observed in the lines

Gabi-i daku'ng bulahan

Ma-u'y oras sa kamahalan.

Noticeably, these provide continuity or a mellifluous quality to the song without hindering the inherent musicality. Instead, they heighten the song's melodious tendency and facilitate the next portion of the song's narrative as in “Gabi-i Daku'ng Bulahan”

Sa pagkatawu siya ni-ambit

Nag-antus sa mga kasakit.

Here, humanity is synonymous with hardships. The extended metaphor nods to the common notion that living is comparable to suffering. The lines signify that the Savior's “pagkatawu” which can either mean “being born into the world” or “to take on man's humanity or position” carry the concomitant implication of suffering, helplessness, despair, etc.

Setting the general mood of the song “Gabi-i Daku'ng Bulahan” as it is sung during Christmas Eve easily reconnects the listeners to the significance of the Christian occasion. Another instance where the same characteristic is observed occurs in the following lines

Iya dayun nga gibiya-an

Ang langit sa ginghari-an

Nana-ug sa kalibutan

which signified the joyous sacrifice of Christ to redeem mankind. The lines imply downright humility as the act “nana-ug sa kalibutan” seems to suggest an effortless leap of emptying oneself that carry tremendous consequences. At times, the same method is employed to preserve the measure, melody, and rhyme of the *daygun*. A nonsensical rhyme is achieved by putting “tempo” and “termino” side by side justifies the need to preserve the song's poetics.

Ug ni-abut na karun ang tempo

Adlaw, bulan, ug termino.

Lauro, M. “Old Cebuano Daygun: Traversing Native Oral and Hispanic Traditions.” *STC College Faculty Journal*, Vol XII, May 2015, pp. 13-32.

Onwards, in the song, the same technique is observed to intensify the denial of lodgings. A sense of drama is established as the lines approach hyperbole to instill desperation. Here, the lines speak for a desperate plea for lodgings that a little nook can do so much for a birthing mother. The phrases “wala’y kasak-an” and “wala’y kaluklukan” intensifies the difficulty of finding for a place to give birth.

Kay dinhi walay kasak-an

Pasabut wala’y kaluklukan

In *Tulo Ka Hari*, the same occurrence is observed and the descriptive vein renders itself particularly useful in leading the listeners to empathize with the Virgin’s unease and the uncertain perils in revealing the newborn babe to the newcomers. The poetic synonyms also proved useful as the words “katahap” and “nagbaka” are seemingly put together to build on the “apprehension” and “worry”; thus, sustaining the emotional backdrop of the narrative.

Bisan sa daku’ng katahap

Ang Birhen wala nagbaka

Ang Niño iya’ng gimbuksan

Sa dayami gikuha-an

In the same *daygun*, the following lines serve to intensify the tension by reminiscing and alluding to King Herod in going after the newborn to kill him. The repetitive ideas infused by the word “mupatay” and the clause “Sa kinabuhi bu-ut mukuha” are indicative of a willful intent to kill a helpless, homeless babe. This supports the idea established earlier on in the narrative that Jesus’ leap for humanity is accompanied by threats and other serious implications against his own helplessness. Again, the poetic synonyms add to the tension while preserving the rhyme and the rhyme scheme in the song.

Bu-ut mupatay sa bata

Sa kinabuhi bu-ut mukuha.

Meanwhile, in the third *daygun*, “Belen”, the lines

Ang pag-gikan namu sa belen

Manamilit sa mahal nga Birhen

resonate with the same vein and function as the other lines in the other *daygun* previously discussed. The last *daygun* which manifests the same characteristic is “Daygun si Hesus” whose lines

Kadtu’ng kamalig nga da-an

Pasilungan sa mga hayupan

recall the *belen* as the shabby and lowly place where the Savior allowed himself to be born – away from impending peril but prone to the cold of the night as the song declares. The ironic situation instills an almost blasphemous accommodation for the babe intended to be the king of kings. Here, the lines concretely use the poetic synonyms to emphasize the backdrop from where the savior is born as it allows the song to flow mellifluously and preserve the rhyme scheme, while keeping the dramatic effect and instilling the desired effect among the audience.

The highly descriptive strain present in the *daygun* is facilitated by the deliberate use of poetic synonyms that in turn enrich the narrative as they increase tension or instill a dramatic effect among listeners. As such, the poetic synonyms help preserve the rhyme and rhyme scheme of the song while sustaining its melody. It helps the audience reconnect to the occasion and to increase empathy among listeners, considering that the *daygun* can relate the message of Christmas better to the audience. The purposeful rendition of the *daygun* in descriptive and narrative formats affirms the presence of orality of early Cebuano poetry in the *daygun* studied. Meanwhile, the narrative content of the *daygun* heavily leans on the Christmas story – an influence of Christianity through colonization. The result is a *daygun* heavily enriched by allusions while framed in an indigenous outline – a proof that Cebuano poetry is enriched by new images and tropes of Hispanic origin.

Repetitive and Formulaic Refrains of the Daygun

Another important characteristic common to the *daygun* is being repetitive and formulaic. In the introduction of *Sugbu-anong Balak Until 1940*, Resil Mojares mentioned that “repetition and reiteration allows the bard time to move from one unit of verse to another as he orally constructs the poem.”⁹ As in indigenous literature, the manifestation of repetition and reiteration in the *daygun* can be safely assumed as its direct link to indigenous literature’s orality. This way, the *daygun* preserves the orality of indigenous literature while it assimilates Hispanic influences. In “Gabi-i Daku’ng Bulahan”, an eight-liner that pertains to the holy family’s search for lodgings countered with rejection is used as a refrain that facilitates the proceeding portion of the narrative. It can be observed that the rhyme scheme dictates the structural division of the poem.

In his Introduction to *Sugbu-anong Balak 1900-1940*, Mojares cites that one of the features of early poetry is the “couplet, which can expand into a longer text.” The following instances given below illustrate that the *daygun* inherits the feature that links it to indigenous literature.

Padayun kamu sa unahan

Kay tu-ay dagha’ng kabalayan

Kay dinhi wala’y kasak-an

Pasabut wala’y kaluklukan

Padayun kamu sa unahan

Kay tu-ay dagha’ng kabalayan

Sa dili pa gani mu-abut

Sa hagdanan gisugat gibalibaran

The beginning two lines in the two stanzas function to achieve parallelism between the fate of the Holy Family as the performer narrates the denial of lodgings on that fateful night and the common plight of carolers on cold nights when homeowners refuse to let them render their carols. The lines are inclusive of the carolers’ similar experiences of looming rejections. Structurally, parallelism is achieved through repetition of the first two lines in both quatrains. This way structural parallelism paves the way for the subjective injunctions of the *daygun*. Consequently, parallelism ties up with the *daygun*’s self-referentiality. In the same *daygun*, another formulaic quatrain is used as conclusion:

Atu na lang kini’ng tapusun

Kini’ng amu nga panagdaygun

Hina-ut pa nga padangatun

Sa tuig nga ingun ni-arun.

This device is more common in three other *daygun*, namely, “Tagbalay”, “Belen”, and “Daygun si Hesus”. In “Tagbalay”, the final quatrain contains a different version from that of “Gabi-i Daku’ng Bulahan”. The first two lines contain a self-referential vein – more applicable to the performers’ position rather than the narrative. These verses pertain to the performance of the *daygun* itself; it lends a sense of “turning inward” as such words indicate a conscious pre closing. It signifies a presentness of both the performer’s realities in relation to the performance of the *daygun* itself. Meanwhile, the second line refers more to man’s temporal existence which is comparable to the short-lived performance of the *daygun*. Consistent with indigenous literature’s orality, the self-referential vein in the *daygun* allows the bard to infuse into it his own realities as it is also appealing to the audience. This imposition is observable as the refrains contain similarities across the *daygun* but are only slightly modified in other *daygun*. As in “Tagbalay” and “Belen”, the following conclusive quatrain is used. It can be observed that the same referential vein is present.

Dili na lang kami magdugay

Sanglit kami lumalabay

Kitang tanan ang maglipay

Maayung Pasko kaninyo, tagbalay.

Finally, in “Daygun si Hesus”, the quatrain departs slightly from the usual formula of the preceding *daygun* and mentions Mary and Joseph and extends a Christmas greeting to the household. This deliberate injunction is a fleeting reminder of Mary’s indispensable role in the birth of the babe. In this particular refrain, the rhyme scheme shows that the *daygun* returns to the couplet as “the basic building unit of Cebuano verse”, which is consistent with early Cebuano poetry. This is observable in the remaining *daygun* “Kandelaria”, “Tulo ka Hari”, and “Oras sa Paglakaw”, which all adhere to indigenous literature.

Sa gihapun sa pagdaygun ta

Si Husep ug si Maria

Si Maria birhen nga ulay

Maayo’ng Pasko tagbalay

In three other *daygun* such as “Kandelaria”, “Tulu ka Hari”, and “Oras sa Paglakaw”, a slightly different formula is used and borrows from a rather liturgical vein. The first line consists of an Old Spanish word for praise. It serves as a subtle reference for “holiness” – an exaltation of the Savior’s holiness. In “Kandelaria”, the quatrain

Alabado kay alabado

Si Hesus ato’ng Ginu-u

Si Maria ma-u ang birhen

Sin Pecado kay amas Amen.

makes a reference to Mary and Jesus and refers to them with an old Spanish word for “holy.” “Tulu ka Hari” is also referred to by the same conclusive quatrain.

Alabado, alabado

Si Hesus ato'ng Ginu-u

Si Maria birhen nga ulay

Ma-ayu'ng Pasko kaninyu tagbalay.

while slightly changing the last line and extending a Christmas greeting, a traditional ending common to most Christmas carols. Lastly, in "Oras sa Paglakaw"

Sa gihapun sa pagdaygun ta

Si Husep ug si Maria

Si Maria ma-u ang Birhen

Sin Pecado kay amas Amen.

The repetitive and formulaic refrains of the *daygun* also speak of the indigenous literature's pervading orality. Repetition allows time for the bard to versify the next lines. In the case of the *daygun*, repetition is used to achieve structural parallelism, to communicate self referentiality, to extend a Christmas greeting, or to impart a liturgical reminder. The variations on how the repetitive refrain is used are a testimony to subjective manipulations of the carolers in such a way that they are able to diversify the uses of a refrain. They are closely linked with self referentiality and therefore, overlap with the bardic role of the carolers. Yet, common to the refrains is a brief mention of the Holy Family, the Virgin Mary, or the passing reminder of life's temporality.

Subjectivity and Self-Referentiality

The last characteristic of the *daygun* that heavily leans on indigenous literature's orality is subjectivity and self-referentiality. This characteristic considers the presence of a voice that slightly departs from the voice in the narrative and which may be safely assumed as the performer's. In this case, the voice extends certain truths and positions which may not only parallel that of the Christmas narrative in the *daygun* but also the current circumstances of the carolers. This particular characteristic overlaps with the repetitive formulas of the refrain as well as the bardic role of the carolers. Noticeable in "Gabi-i Daku'ng Bulahan" is the declarative demeanor in the following lines. This indicates bringing the *daygun* to end at will. The conclusive quatrain is rather wistful and hopeful for future accommodation.

Atu na lang kini-ng tapusun

Kini'ng amu nga panagdaygun

Hina-ut pa nga padangatun

Sa tu-ig nga ingun ni-arun.

Similar formulas occur across the four *daygun* with slight variations. These variations occur in the first two lines of the *daygun*. In “Kandelaria”, it is rendered as “Alabado kay alabado/Si Hesus atu’ng Ginu-u” whereas in “Oras sa Paglakaw”, it is rendered as “Sa gihapun sa pagdaygoun ta/Si Husep ug si Maria” but ending with the same couplet. The following quatrain occurs in “Kandelaria” and “Oras sa Paglakaw”, which goes to show that alterations are subjective injunctions of the carolers.

Alabado kay alabado

Si Hesus ato’ng Ginu-u

Si Maria ma-u ang birhen

Sin Pecado kay amas Amen.

Meanwhile, “Tulu ka Hari” and “Daygun si Hesus” reiterate the first two lines, differing only in the final two lines. The nonsensical rhyme that concludes the song may have been intended to preserve the rhyme scheme. It is marked with the terminal rhyme using the diphthong /ay/ in “ulay” and “tagbalay” which do not invoke any conceptual significance.

Si Maria birhen nga ulay

Maayu’ng Pasko kaninyu tagbalay.

Subjectivity and self-reflexivity affirms the presence of the carolers in the *daygun*, which by extension strengthens its orality. The subjective injunctions of the carolers infuse nonsensical rhyme, preserve the rhyme scheme, and maintain the musicality of the *daygun*. These injunctions also prove that the realities present in the carolers’ life are hardly removed from their craft.

The Bardic Role of the Carolers

The performance of the *daygun* brings to the surface some parallelisms with the performance of Western epics on three counts: the performer, the accompaniment, and the purpose. The carolers’ role may be likened to that of a traditional bard who travels to places to impart the Christmas narrative through a song with the accompaniment of the guitar. Whereas bards from Western countries sing with the harp, the carolers preserve the practice by serenading other households. Whereas bards sing about a great warrior and his deeds and by extension preserve culture orally, the carolers sing of Jesus’ infancy narratives. Perhaps the most important bardic role that the carolers incidentally fulfill is that of preserving the no tangible heritage of the *daygun*. This is very Lauro, M. “Old Cebuano Daygun: Traversing Native Oral and Hispanic Traditions.” *STC College Faculty Journal*, Vol XII, May 2015, pp. 13-32.

much similar to the singing of the epic by minstrels that allow them to preserve the culture of their society. Noteworthy is the performance of the *daygun* in exchange for any amount. Perhaps, the economic intent associated with the performance of the *daygun* sets it apart from the performance of the epic in meadhalls. Another distinction that sets the *daygun* apart from western epics is that the adaptation and recreation occurs in the tune of the *daygun* rather than in the content, which varies from performance to performance. The carolers have claimed the *daygun* can be sung with 17 possible tonal variations. The content remains constant because the *daygun* is derived from a written source. Yet, its performance is a concoction of both the oral Cebuano poetry and the Hispanic.

The Hispanic Strain: Allusion-Based

Four of the seven *daygun* also bear allusion to the Biblical narrative of Jesus' infancy. The *daygun* narrate the conception, birth, presentation and even the finding of Jesus in the temple. Specifically, "Gabi-i Daku'ng Bulahan" speaks of the holy family's search for lodgings and Jesus' birth. The two *daygun*, "Gabi-i Dakung Bulahan" and "Kandelaria", purposely established Mary's role in giving birth to Jesus as in

Nana-ug ang Esp'rito Santo

Gilalang kini'ng mistiryu

Gipalampus sa Mahal nga Birhen

Ang gi-anak didtu sa belen.

The lines apparently heralded the Virgin's position and this is contrasted to Eve's sinful disobedience. This representation shows that allusions dictate certain stereotypes. Eve is recalled and stereotyped as the "bringer or origin of the sins of mankind" as opposed to the exalted position of the Virgin Mary. The intentional reduction of "gayud" or "gyud" to "gid" must have been purposely done to preserve the song's melody. Even the word "Esp'rito Santo" has a vowel sound purposely reduced.

Ka'tung kaliwat ni Eba

Nagadala gid sa mga sala.

The same lines recur in "Kandelaria". In the first *daygun*, "Gabi-i Daku'ng Bulahan", an allusion to the Annunciation narrative is apparent in the following lines while preserving the enigmatic quality of indigenous poetry. The brevity of the lines that capture the allusion adds to the mysterious quality common to indigenous poetry. Specifically, the line "Gilalang kini'ng mistiryu" is pure poetry. In itself, it is a reference to the totality of the Annunciation captured only in three words.

Nana-ug ang Esp'rito Santo

Lauro, M. "Old Cebuano Daygun: Traversing Native Oral and Hispanic Traditions." *STC College Faculty Journal*, Vol XII, May 2015, pp. 13-32.

Gilalang kini'ng mistiryu.

In "Kandelaria", the lines

Gidala kini'ng Ginu-u

Didtu ni-adtu nga templo

Sa templo sa Herusalem

Gipresentar ug gihalaran

recall the Presentation of the Child Jesus. In essence, the entire *daygun* may be reduced to the sole allusion. Meanwhile, the next two lines allude to the famous image of the Judgment narrated in catechism classes and inculcated early on during childhood as an important reminder that no sin goes unpunished.

Gitigum ang sala nga tanan

Sa censu ni Abraham.

In "Oras sa Paglakaw", the next four lines allude to the narrative when the young Jesus figured in discussions inside the temple with details faithful to the Biblical version.

Kay sa iya nga pagkawala

Ni Maria nga gipangita

Ang Niño didto nipuli

Sa templo sa mga doktore

Na sa ba sa nga panaglalis.

Meanwhile, "Daygun si Hesus" briefly narrates Mary's Annunciation

Si Maria ang inahan

Gipili sa Diyos nga Amahan

Kay sa anghel gipakunsaran

Kining babayi'ng palaran.

In the same *daygun*, another allusion is a clear foreboding of what is to come and is juxtaposed in consonance with the celebration of the birth of the babe.

Sa belen siya gihugus

Sa Kalbaryo siya matapus.

The allusions range from the conception to the birth of Jesus, the presentation, and even to the death of the savior. It is noteworthy to mention that allusions dictate stereotypical conventions as they set the ideal and inferior representations of the two women, Eve and the Virgin Mary. These allusions affirm that images and tropes enrich the native tradition (3). The manner by which the foreign images and tropes have permeated the indigenous frame of the *daygun* is what is referred to by Casper (14) as “‘cooptation’ or ‘creative deformation’ of folk forms by the Spaniards which had its equivalent in the native naturalization of foreign forms”. Mojares (3) claims that one does not find (as in modern poetry) the more strictly demarcated boundaries between texts. Here, the *daygun* manifests two streams of traditions: the Hispanic as evidenced by the allusions of the Christmas narrative and the indigenous, manifested by the Cebuano-Visayan expression.

Rhyme Scheme and Meter

The seven *daygun* follow a regular rhyme scheme with the quatrain as the basic unit. This is evidenced by the frequency of the rhyme scheme that later formed the structural outline of the *daygun*. This nods to the claim that the basic unit of indigenous poetry is the couplet but may be extended to a longer poem (Mojares, 3). However, the persisting rhyme scheme is a Hispanic influence as indigenous poetry does not follow a strict rhyme scheme. Common to the seven *daygun* is the syllabic measure that runs from seven to twelve syllables with the eight syllabic (octosyllabic) and the nine-syllabic measure as the most common. This is an affirmation of the claim that indigenous poetry follows the 7-12 line measure. In “Gabi-i Daku’ng Bulahan” the first 20 lines follow aaaabbbbbaaaaccccdddd. Noticeably, lines 25-32 have the longest uniform scheme of cccccc. Certain breaks from the regularity of the rhyme scheme facilitate transitions in the narrative, so these irregularities are considered facilitative rather than destructive.

Gipanamkun sa Mahal nga Birhen (e)

Ang gi-anak didtu sa belen (e)

Ang ka-ulay wala’y pagbalhin (e)

'Ning kahimtang sa dayami (f)

Onwards in the song, a formulaic refrain is inserted that facilitates the next portion of the narrative. Within the refrain is a noticeable break in the rhyme scheme.

Padayun kamu sa unahan (a)

Kay tu-ay dagha'ng kabalayan (a)

Kay dinhi wala'y kasak-an (a)

Pasabut wala'y kaluklukan (a)

Padayun kamu sa unahan (a)

Kay tu-ay dagha'ng kabalayan (a)

Sa dili pa gani mu-abut (k)

Sa hagdanan gisugat, gibalibaran (a)

Meanwhile, the meter ranges from 7-12 syllables – a close semblance to the meter of indigenous poetry.

In another *daygun*, “Kandelaria,” the rhyme scheme is regular and more consistent than the rest of the *daygun*. Its meter ranges from 7-10 syllables to a foot, while its final quatrain has bbcc.

Alabado kay alabado (b)

Si Hesus atu'ng Ginu-u (b)

Si Maria ma-u ang birhen (c)

Sin Pecado kay amas Amen. (c)

“Tulu Ka Hari” includes a quoted statement without altering the rhyme scheme. Here, too, the wise men who located the baby Jesus showed a considerable amount of humility on par with that of the king of kings who entered the human state. They remove their scepters and their crowns to worship a king higher than they – an act to try to prove their worth.

Bisan daku ang kabalaka (b)

Ning-dayun pagsulud sila (b)

Ang septro ug ang korona (b)

Gikuha sa ulu nila (b)

Sa pag-adtu kanila (b)

Sa Birhen Santa Maria (b)

Nag-apud pagpangutana (b)

“Senyora, may anak ka ba?” (b)

Onwards, in the song, a longer narration of consistent scheme talks about the gifts offered to the newborn king. One by one, the gifts are discussed with their symbolic meaning.

Sa dayun nila ug buka (a)

Kang Baltazar ma-u ang mira (b)

Sa putus nga ila’ng dala (a)

Kapa-it nga wala’y sama (b)

Bulawan, insenso, ug mira (a)

Tima-an sa pagkatawo niya (b)

Nga sa Niño ila’ng gidala (a)

Manunubos sa mga sala 'ta (b)

Kang Melchor ang bulawan (j)

Natapus nanghalad sila (b)

Gihalad niya sa tuman (j)

Sa dala nila nga gasa (b)

Tima-an sa pagkabantugan (j)

Sila'ng tulo ang nangaliya (b)

Sa tibu-uk nga kalibutan (j)

Kang Husep ug kang Maria (b)

Kang Gaspar ang insenso (k)

Ihalad niya sa Niño (k)

Tima-an sa pagkatawo (k)

Sa pagka-Diyos ug Ginu-u (k)

Consistent with the other *daygon*, “Tulo Ka Hari” has seven syllables as the shortest meter, and 11 beats as the longest meter.

“Oras sa Paglakaw” also follows a regular scheme whose meter ranges from 7-11 beats.

“Belen” is a shortened version of the Christmas narrative. It talks about leaving the *belen* and finding the way back. “Belen” is the shortest *daygun* with only 20 lines because the carolers deliberately shortened it. It follows the 8-10 meter which is still within the measure of indigenous poetry.

On the other hand, the assonantal rhyme present in indigenous poetry is also present in the *daygun*. It is apparent in the following instances in “Gabi-i Daku’ng Bulahan” and “Kandelaria” respectively.

Usa ra ka panaptun nga diyutay

Ang gipilipit sa iyang tiyan

Nagkurug sa kabugnaw

...

Kasing-kasing halos matunaw

Nagasud-ung sa pagtan-aw

Arun kita mu-ila na

...

Tungud lang sa mga sala ‘ta

Atu na lang kini’ng tapusun

...

Sa tu-ig nga ingun ni-arun.

Borrowed Hispanic Words

Among the Hispanic words which are found across the *daygun* include

alabado	mistiryo
anghel	nubida
belen	oras
birhen	perdon

censu	pista
doktores	pobre
gipresentar	propeta
giselibrar	puerta
grasya	rasones
husto	septro
insenso	templo
korona	termino
merbo	lisensya
mira.	

These words are localized and are used to mean what they originally mean in Spanish. The word “alabado” means “to be holy” in Spanish. Meanwhile, in the *daygun* “Tulo ka Hari” the Virgin is addressed with “Señora”, a respectable title given to women. The word “doktores” is clearly a derivative that means “expert”. The words, “gipresentar” and “giselibrar” are Cebuano derivatives of the Spanish “celebrar” and “presentar” that mean “to celebrate” and “to present” in English. They are used side by side with native Cebuano words. Meanwhile, the word “nubida” is closest to the colloquial Spanish “movida” that means “occurrence or affair” (<http://www.wordreference.com>). So, to say “Ni-ay dala namo nga gasa/ Mahinuklugu’ng nubida” refers to the rendition of the *daygun* as an offering to homeowners – a rather sanctified performance of Jesus’ narrative. The word “perdon” may have been a derivative of “pardon” since its use in the line “Mangayu kami ug perdon/Kung masayup pasaylu-un” indicate an apologetic expression. Also, the *daygun* includes forms of address in Spanish as in “Niño” and “Señora” to mean the baby Jesus and the Virgin Mary, respectively.

Meanwhile, the *daygun* also contains a proliferation of Cebuano-Visayan words unusually heard of in everyday conversations especially among modern speakers. Such words include

banyaga	nagapala
bililhun	nanag-apud
bug-us	nangaliya
bulahan	natad
diyutay	natahap/katahap
dulum-dumun	ni-ambit
gihugus	padangatun

gikabtan	pag-asuyun
gilalang	pagatuki-un
gipakunsaran	pagkabantugan
gipamulungan	pagpasipala
gipanamkun	pagtutima-an
gisilbi	palaran
hipalgan	pulung
kaluklukan	sabyu
kamahalan	sanglit
kasamahan	sanglitan
kina-adman	sulugu-un
lumalabay	talahunun
ma-anyag	tampalasan
mahinuklugun'g	tinguha
manamilit	tulutawgun
manglakat	ulay
matahum	umunanuy
nagalakat	

Words like *nagalakat/manglakat* are northern variants of *naglakaw/manglakaw* which means “to walk”. These words can still be heard among speakers in the northernmost part of the province like Bantayan Island and Camotes Island. *Dulumdumun* may be a derivative of *paghandum* or *dumdum* which can mean “to remember or recall” or “to find or locate” *Umunanuy* pertains to how Joseph walked toward the tree and could mean “to walk very slowly and reflectively”. The word *tulutawgun* is used to mean “to hail or summon”. Meanwhile, the word “sabyo” literally means “sage; a mentor in spiritual and philosophical topics who is renowned for profound wisdom” (<http://www.binisaya.com>). Another entry relates the meaning to the three sages of the New Testament (Melchor, Gaspar, and Balthazar). To say “kahayag sa mga sabyu” then is a figurative reference to the divine light radiated by the wise men in visiting the *belen*.

Conclusion

The *daygun* is a product of both indigenous and Hispanic traditions. The characteristics of being narrative and descriptive, repetitive and formulaic, as well as subjectivity and self referentiality adhere to the characteristics commonly manifested by oral indigenous literature. The performance of the *daygun* also carries the bardic role of the carolers. Though the *daygun* is entirely faithful to the Annunciation and infancy narratives of Jesus, the fact remains that the performance of the *daygun* lends the carolers their *bardic* role but its content remains unchanged. In considering the *daygun* as a musico-poetic repertoire, the bardic role of the carolers is shifted to modifying the accompanying tone of the *daygun*. Meanwhile, the allusions present in the *daygun* adhere closely to the Annunciation, Presentation, finding of Jesus, and the role played by Mary in the birth of Jesus, among others.

The end-rhyme is a telling illustration of the Hispanic tradition that permeated the indigenous poetic structure since the meter closely resembles the traditional 7-12 syllable per line with the eight syllable count (octosyllabic) and the nine syllable count per line as the most common. The assonantal rhyme is also very much evident in some *daygun*.

The loan words prove that indeed the Spanish language has so permeated the daily lingo of the Cebuanos because it is used side by side with the Cebuano-Visayan language.

Works Cited

Alburo, Erlinda K. et. al. ed. *Cebuano Poetry Sugboanong Balak 1900-1940*. 1988. Cebu City: Cebu Star Press.

Canave-Dioquino, Corazon. *Folk Traditions*. National Commission for Culture and the Arts. 19 Sep 2014. <http://www.ncca.gov.ph/about-culture-and-arts/articles-on-c-n-a/article.php?igm=1&i=151>

Casper, Leonard. *The Opposing Thumb: Decoding Literature of the Marcos Regime*. 1995. Quezon City: Giraffe Books.

Mojares, Resil B. Introduction. *Cebuano Poetry Sugbu-anong Balak 1900-1940*. 1988. By Alburo, Erlinda K. et al. Cebu Star Press.

Pooley, Robert C. et. al. ed. *England in Literature*. 1963. Chicago: Scott, Foresman and Company.

Santos, Ramon P. *Constructing a National Identity through Music*. National Commission for Culture and Arts. 13 Jun 2003. 19 Sep 2014. <http://ncca.gov.ph/about-culture-and-arts/articles-on-c-n-a/article.php?subcat=13&i=60>

<http://www.binisaya.com/>

<http://www.wordreference.com/>